

Case Study

Identifying and Ranking of Barriers for Activity of Export Management Companies (Case study: Khorasan Razavi Province)

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Abstract

Economic and industrial progress, coupled with heightened global competition, has turned market access and retention into intricate challenges. Within this context, a notable portion of businesses and trade practitioners, facing issues due to their specialization and high costs, encounter various hurdles when entering and sustaining positions in global markets. The utilization of export intermediaries, particularly export management companies, stands as a successful global experience and a potential tool for addressing a significant portion of export-related problems. The present study, of a descriptive-survey nature, employs a mixed (quantitative-qualitative) approach with the goal of identifying and ranking barriers faced by export management companies. To achieve this, a purposefully selected sample of experts in the export domain underwent specialized interviews, and after theoretical saturation, barriers were categorized into six titles and two overarching groups: intra-organizational and extra-organizational. The data were then ranked using a questionnaire and, finally, through the Friedman test. The ranking results reveal that skill and management barriers resulting from intra-organizational factors hold the highest importance, securing the first and second positions. Following these, three other barriers from the extra-organizational factors, centered around governance and policy-making, common factors, and those originating from the exporting community, respectively, rank third to fifth. Lastly, barriers with performance origins from the intra-organizational factors secure the sixth position.

Keywords: Export development, Export intermediary, Export management company.

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Introduction

According to some economists including Smith² export are one of the most important factors in the economic growth of countries. According to these economists, when a country's export increase, it increasingly leads to the growth of the domestic economy (Pourashraf, 2014). A brief review of export development patterns among successful countries in the world also indicates a deep relationship between exports and economic growth in those countries (Parliament Research Center Of IRAN, 2020). Additionally, Okun et al. (2010) consider export development to be the driving engine of economic growth and sustainable development, and they regard continuous presence in international markets as politically and economically significant for many countries, viewing it as an important indicator in evaluating their international performance.

Now that export have gained importance as one of the key indicators of economic growth and prosperity, it is necessary, alongside understanding the internal influencing factors, to study and emulate successful countries, and to aim for the formulation of a comprehensive and effective export development plan. The existence of an appropriate trade strategy that ensures proper interaction with the global economy allows export sector activists to benefit from better and more reliable planning in marketing their products and increasing production. Therefore, trade policies should while maintaining a stable long-term trend, also focus on achieving more and higher-quality interactions with target countries (Noori, 2023).

Exporting and selling goods in foreign markets have specific nuances and sensitivities that, if neglected may lead to the failure of the export process. Planning to maintain export markets and develop export requires understanding both the current state of export capabilities and the foreign customers (Parliament Research Center Of IRAN, 2020).

The increase in global competition has led many companies to seek opportunities to enter international markets and establish a position in them. However, success in foreign markets is not easy due to cultural differences, intense competition and the increasing dynamism of the market (Larimo, 2007). According to him, export performance is considered a multidimensional and complex concept, influenced by various variables such as managerial characteristics, managerial attitudes and perceptions, industry characteristics, target market characteristics and strategies related to export marketing. Additionally, research by Safari and SalmanSaleh (2019) shows that the number of SMEs engaged in export activities has significantly increased with technological advancements.

Entrepreneurs and managers need to make important decisions regarding market selection, entry methods, and competitive strategies to enter foreign markets (Kogut, 2002). The decision-making process can be challenging because the uncertainty prevailing in the market environment can make the external environment more complex and distinct from the national environment (Liesch et al., 2011).

OECD and APEC (2007) conducted a survey and concluded that inactive exporters face problems such as finding markets and opportunities, and identifying foreign

² Medina-Smith, E. J. (2000)

customers, whereas active exporters face challenges arising from tariffs, currency, regulations and competition. This is in line with the findings of Pinho and Martin (2010), who concluded that the perceived challenges are not the same for non-exporters and exporters. For instance, non-exporters are concerned about the lack of information on prospective markets, a lack of staff with foreign experience, a lack of technical skills, and inadequate governmental and financial support. In contrast, exporters see the other challenges as the main ones, such as identifying the target market, warehousing and control of the physical product flow (Pinho and Martin, 2010).

The key factors influencing export performance are divided into two categories that need to be evaluated separately: internal factors and external environmental characteristics (Agnihotri and Bhattacharya, 2015). Internal factors include company-related and product-related characteristics, while external factors include industry-level characteristics and determinants of the export market (Cavusgil and Zou, 1994). Similarly, Leonidou (2004) argues that the export barriers faced by SMEs should be divided into internal barriers (such as marketing barriers) and external barriers (such as governmental and environmental barriers).

Gharehche and Shamshiri (2010) also consider two factors to be involved in export development programs. One is information as a strategic tool needed by economic enterprises at various levels of the internationalization process, and the other is a cohesive network of actors and institutions involved in export development programs. According to them, these two factors are interdependent and must be both efficient and effective in practice to lead to a successful export development program and pave the way for active economic enterprises to move towards international markets.

Therefore, given the complexity of the matter and the presence of competitive sensitivities, correct decision-making has become highly important. The lack of financial and human resources for export management, investors prioritizing to the provision of raw materials, insufficient attention to marketing and limited knowledge about markets are the most significant weaknesses of industries particularly SMEs at present. This means that SMEs due to these limitations cannot independently provide the financial and informational resources necessary to manage their international business activities. Thus one of the tools employed in many countries to enter global markets and increase export of these enterprises at least initially is the use of an export intermediary service (Okun et al., 2010).

Based on the opinion of Suwannarat (2016) and Okun et al. (2010), export intermediary companies act as facilitators of export, reducing customers' export costs including research, negotiation, supervision, and implementation expenses.

Parliament Research Center Of IRAN (2020) In its report identifies one of the main obstacles to export related to export processes and exporter characteristics and believes that encouraging small exporters to use export intermediary services can significantly alleviate these barriers. The Trade Promotion Organization of Iran (TPO) also recognizes export intermediaries as a highly effective tool in achieving export development for businesses and referring to the experiences of various countries such as Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Turkey, the United States, Canada and others it emphasizes that establishing

an active and close relationship between economic enterprises and export intermediaries can contribute significantly to export development in societies highlighting this aspect as worthy of attention.

One type of export intermediary is Export Management Companies (EMCs) (Balabanis, 2000, 2001, 2005; Bello and Williamson, 1985) which play a role in assisting economic enterprises in entering global markets. These companies can take on either full or partial management of export activities for businesses especially SMEs depending on the conditions and needs of their clients (Noori, 2023).

Based on the experience of various countries such as the United States, Canada, Japan, Singapore, Turkey, South Korea, etc, it has been established that each society can benefit from close relationships between economic enterprises and Export Management Companies and policymakers play a pivotal role in facilitating such relationships (Hosseini Gorjaji and Mirzaei, 2016).

Export Management Companies provide services to export-oriented businesses in identifying demand in international markets and facilitating proper processing and response to that demand (facilitating foreign trade) that as a result, both economic enterprises benefit from entering global markets and the export management company profits from establishing a long-term relationship between the exporter and the buyer. The synergistic outcome of this relationship contributes to achieving a key economic development goal, namely the expansion of non-oil exports (Dadkhah et al., 2019).

The challenges in the field of foreign trade especially exports, can be broadly categorized into two main groups: internal and external issues, which together present significant complexities and difficulties in the process of forming and expanding export for businesses particularly SMEs. Despite recent years seeing the impact of external sanctions as a notable external factor affecting our country's foreign trade, the presence of diverse facilities and considerable domestic potentials, coupled with leveraging their synergies, means that achieving export expansion and earning foreign currency is not beyond reach and effective measures can indeed be taken in this regard. Therefore, precise identification of barriers and problems within the export sector and among exporters and taking action to address them, is more crucial than ever (Noori, 2023).

Exporting is a specialized and costly process and a significant portion of domestic exporters and SMEs face multiple challenges such as lack of export knowledge and inadequate management capabilities in related processes, insufficient financial resources and weaknesses in marketing and selling their products. Therefore, the presence of Export Management Companies alongside them through various actions such as providing consultancy and market studies, participating in international exhibitions, accepting exports on their behalf and more can reduce the risks of entering diverse foreign markets. This support can lead to successful market entry and enhance the competitive capabilities of these enterprises in the field of export (Abor, 2011; Czinkota, 2009).

In a final summary, it can be stated that since export continue to be accepted as a viable strategy for internationalization in economic and commercial dimensions, engaging with EMCs is considered crucial and vital. These companies, recognized globally as

experienced and useful tools facilitate the understanding of target export markets. This interaction is deemed significant for businesses aiming to expand internationally as it enables them to navigate the complexities of foreign markets effectively. Research conducted by researcher indicates that there have been very few studies on the subject of export intermediaries, particularly Export Management Companies, in Iran. Therefore, it is necessary and justifiable to deal with the issue of Export Management Companies, considering their important roles and functions, with the aim of identifying quantitative and qualitative development barriers and proposing solutions to solve them. Accordingly, this study try to identifying barriers for activities of Export Management Companies, prioritize them and provide strategies to remove barriers and enhance their performance. Moreover, decision-makers involved in export are increasingly familiarizing themselves with the challenges confronting Export Management Companies, thereby gaining the necessary awareness to mitigate these challenges and improve export capabilities for these entities.

The aim of this research is to identifying and ranking the barriers faced by Export Management Companies. Consequently, the corresponding objectives and questions are as follows:

Main Objective: Identifying the barriers faced by Export Management Companies.

Sub-objectives:

1. Rank the barriers faced by Export Management Companies.
2. Provide solutions to improve the activities of Export Management Companies.

Main Question: What are the barriers faced by export management companies?

Sub-questions:

1. How can the barriers faced by Export Management Companies be prioritized?
2. What proposed solutions can improve the activities of Export Management Companies?

This study focuses on Export Management Companies particularly those located in Khorasan Razavi province in 2023.

Theoretical Framework and Research Background

Export Development

The role and importance of export growth in the economic development process is fully recognized. Export development provides foreign exchange resources for economic development and can play a decisive role in the formation of economic structures, optimal allocation of resources, utilization of economies of production scale, achievement of international specialization and more (Rahmani et al., 2008).

Gençtürk and Kotabe (2001) refer to the set of policies and public programs designed to assist firms' export activities such as consulting, tax incentives and export financing, organizing and participating in trade exhibitions, helping to increase sales and similar efforts as export development programs.

Moshabaki et al. (2012) also state that the goal of export development programs is to increase export performance by enhancing the capabilities, resources, strategies and overall competitiveness of firms which leads to improved export performance. Another major goal of export development programs from their perspective can be to increase a country's foreign revenues in order to improve its trade balance. Thus, in summary export development can be described as all actions and strategies that lead to quantitative and qualitative improvement and development in a country's export activities.

Many businesses due to a lack of experience, limited resources, or other problems, cannot or do not want to pursue exports extensively. Governments by formulating and implementing export development programs can help them overcome these limitations and play a key role in encouraging their foreign trade activities through export incentives in the form of programs or supportive financial institutions such as export development banks. These programs while enhancing export performance and generating foreign exchange, provide a ready external source for acquiring information, experiences and necessary knowledge and create new capacity to deal with the complexities of exporting. (Hanzal Eidani, 2017).

Export Intermediaries

An export intermediary are specialized entities that operates as export organizations representing several non-competitive producers (Root, 1994). Many intermediaries are considered part of the indirect export method and each group has different advantages. Indirect export methods can be distinguished based on the location of intermediaries' activities and whether they act for themselves, producers, or buyers (Onkvisit & Shaw, 2007). Success in exports according to (Spencer, 1994), requires expertise in executive procedures and having sufficient financial resources. He believes that even the most experienced exporters lack sufficient self-confidence in their knowledge about shipping arrangements and payment methods. Suwanarat (2016) also contends that export intermediary companies as facilitators of export activities, reduce the export costs of their clients including research, negotiation, supervision and execution.

The spectrum of challenges faced by companies, especially SMEs in entering international markets and the field of export is highly noteworthy (Loane et al., 2004) and export marketing of domestic products is challenging due to various factors such as geographical distance, cultural differences, and communication problems even for successful and prominent companies on the global stage. (Howard, 1994; Moore, 1990). Therefore, these companies utilize export intermediaries which fall into the category of indirect export methods to export their products (DeNoble et al., 1989).

Dadkhah et al., (2019) state that any experts believe that export intermediaries play a crucial role in in helping exporters enter into global markets and provide valuable services in the field of exports by acting as intermediaries between individuals and organizations.

Export intermediary companies as export facilitators reduce the export costs of their clients including search, negotiation, supervision and implementation costs. They generally provide two categories of services to economic enterprises especially SMEs that are aimed at overcoming internal challenges of export which include: relationship-building services (establishing connections) and services related to processing and responding to customer needs.

Entry into International Markets

Today, companies are inevitably compelled to make strategic decisions in the field of international marketing operations. Initially, they must decide whether to enter or not enter the international trade arena. Following a positive decision, they need to determine the location and geographical positioning. Subsequently, they should specify their market entry strategy. Furthermore, decisions should be made regarding the international marketing mix program, designing and formulating the competitive strategy (BabaeiZakliki, 2017).

Although according to Kotler and Armstrong (2020) not all companies are required to enter global markets to survive, there are various factors that drive companies to internationalize its operations. Each of these factors alone can provide the motivation for such actions. Before venturing abroad, every company must carefully assess both the potential risks and rewards and answer multiple questions regarding their capability for global operations. Based on the research by Haghighi (2021) companies fundamentally face three key decisions when considering entry into foreign markets: which markets to enter, when to enter and at what scale or size to enter foreign markets.

BabaeiZakliki (2017) believes that companies have numerous reasons for deciding to enter international markets. Some are motivated by a desire to align with the political aspects of global trade while others are driven by opportunities or competitive challenges. He lists various reasons for engaging in international business activities, including: Seizing opportunities, Pursuing Customers, Market exploration, Expanding Activities, High Economic Growth Rates in Other Countries, Benefiting from the Advantages from Product Life Cycle Differences, Cost Factor and The Only Feasible Strategy.

Strategies for Entering International Markets

Sharma and Erramili (2004) consider entering international markets as a systematic organization that involves a company transferring its products, technology, human resources, management experiences and other resources to other countries. This decision is among the key strategic decisions in the international marketing domain and determines the type of company activities, including production and marketing, mixed management and foreign market investment.

Research findings indicate that there are different classifications for methods of entering international markets. In one primary classification, entry methods into international markets are categorized into three main focuses: export-oriented, contract-oriented and capital-oriented. In another classification entry methods into international

markets are categorized based on the ownership share that the company aims to have in the process of entering foreign markets (Dadkhah et al.2019).

Export-Oriented Approach

One of the growth strategies that companies employ when venturing into international markets is exportation that contributes to national economic performance by enhancing capabilities, expertise and knowledge (Ebrahimi, 2021). Exporting is the simplest means of entering a foreign market and has consistently proven to be the best method for initiating marketing activities beyond national borders (Keegan and Green, 2000). Exportation is a well-established and time-tested method in international trade. Many manufacturing companies have commenced their international endeavors by exporting goods and later gradually adopted additional methods for entering foreign markets (Haghighi, 2021).

Export operations are generally classified into two main categories: direct and indirect and according to Dadkhah et al. (2019) the selection and utilization of these methods depend on various important factors such as marketing objectives, producer's resources and experiences, the availability and capabilities of intermediaries, product and customer characteristics, market environment and control. According to the definition provided by Onkvisit & Shaw (2004) direct exportation occurs through direct sales to agents or retailers in the target markets, while indirect export happens through sales to distribution agents in the home country or the country of origin. In other words, if the sale of goods to the foreign market is managed through local intermediaries in the destination country, it is called direct export and if the sale of goods to the foreign market is done through an agent or intermediary in the country of origin, it is called indirect export. (BabaeiZakliki, 2017).

Contract-Based Approaches

According to Cateora & Graham (2019) contractual agreements refer to non-equity long-term collaborations between companies in foreign markets. Under contractual agreements various elements such as technology, processes, trademarks or human skills are typically transferred. Contractual agreements include: Comprehensive licensing (license), Limited licensing (franchise), Joint venture and Consortium (BabaeiZakliki, 2017).

Capital-Based Approaches

In another classification of strategies for entering foreign markets based on the type of investment, two main categories emerge: Direct investment and Indirect investment. In direct investment which occurs within a foreign country, companies may focus on factors such as cheap labor, avoiding heavy import taxes, reducing transportation costs to target markets and direct access to raw materials. In indirect investment, the company's commitment to international business activities is minimal (BabaeiZakliki, 2017).

Ownership Approaches

This approach is one of the most recognized classifications enjoying greater comprehensiveness, acceptance and applicability compared to other approaches. In this approach the level of ownership share that a company is willing to have in the process of entering foreign markets is considered. It includes two sections: ownership-granting and non-ownership-granting where EMCs as an export intermediaries fall under non-ownership-granting category (Dadkhah et al., 2019).

Export Management Company (EMC)

According to Brasch (1978) definition these companies are marketing institutions that instead of customizing the products of suppliers for various foreign markets. Additionally he believes that an EMC is a type of export intermediary that plays a role in assisting economic enterprises in entering global markets and depending on conditions and needs can take on the management of all or part of the export activities of SMEs. Daniels and Radebaugh (2004) also assert that EMCs as export units provide a wide range of services such as market analysis, documentation, financial and legal services, purchasing and reselling, representation, extensive research in target markets, advertising, promotions, transportation and essential recommendations regarding support for the spiritual assets and information gathering about the creditworthiness of foreign customers, etc. for one or several producers of non-competitive goods. Czinkota & Ronkainen (2013) introduce EMCs as small domestic entities that using international marketing expertise in specific regions, act as representatives or distributors, providing international marketing services for a considerable number of companies.

The services of an EMC cover a broad spectrum of export processes and according to the report of the Trade Promotion Organization of Iran (TPO) these services are generally divided into two categories: 1) buyer-centric services (Services related to creating demand in international markets, including market research to identify the target market, determining the qualitative features of products required by the target market, assistance in formulating marketing and advertising strategies, identifying and selecting distributors, negotiations for obtaining licenses, training on marketing each product to distributors, and providing after-sales services), 2) seller-centric services (Services aimed at meeting the demand of international customers, including preparing the necessary documents and paperwork for exports, branding and packaging of export products, accurate cost calculations, warehousing services, coordination of transportation affairs, quality control of products, financial and risk management).

Additionally, Haigh (1994) lists other services under the title “usual services of an export management company” including participation in international exhibitions, product displays and consultancy in protecting trademarks and licensing. According to Rameshan & Soutar (1996) entering foreign markets through EMCs brings the following advantages to the companies involved: 1) Elimination of the expenses associated with establishing an export unit, 2) Rapid entry into international markets facilitated by the existing export infrastructure of the EMC, 3) prevention of losses for inexperienced or less experienced companies through actions such as advertising, promotions, market research and selecting the best distribution channels for sending

products to the foreign market by the export management company, 4) Access to legal advice from the EMC on matters like the registration and protection of intellectual property rights, exploitation, trademarks and etc., 5) Leveraging the experience and expertise of the EMC resulting in a faster and more efficient learning curve for entering foreign markets, 6) Potential for increased sales of products in foreign markets through the diversified product portfolio managed by the EMC, 7) Cost savings in transportation expenses due to the EMC's ability to efficiently handle various shipments.

As per the report of the Trade Promotion Organization of Iran (TPO) various export development programs effectively strengthen SMEs and create a suitable environment for the formation and development of EMCs. Governments can utilize EMCs as a tool to expand their penetration into foreign markets. Depending on the level of commitment governments are willing to undertake different approaches toward EMCs take shape. These approaches include: 1) Raising public awareness about the nature and objectives of EMCs and their role in export development, 2) Providing incentives and motivational resources to facilitate the establishment of EMCs when there is insufficient inclination or competency in the private sector and 3) The government itself takes action to establish EMCs in order to expand the exports of SMEs.

Based on the experiences of other countries in establishing EMCs, the quantitative development of these companies and export consortia is considered as a model for export development in all countries. However, certain ideological issues and legal challenges in Iran have made the path to the formation and development of these companies difficult and uneven (Nikan, 2017).

In Iran TPO has implemented a monitoring and ranking system for companies engaged in export services aiming to standardize and enhance their development. According to this system, companies are classified into three grades (Rank 1, Rank 2, and Rank 3) based on a set of indicators provided by the TPO. Evaluations indicate that in the years leading up to this research, both ranked and unranked EMCs have shown a declining trend in both quantitative and qualitative aspects that need serious attention from officials and policymakers in this domain. The current status of EMCs as of the time of this study and based on information available on the official website of the TPO is outlined below:

Table 1. Ranking Status of EMCs in Iran

Fundamental Approval	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Total
11	0	1	4	16

Source: Trade Promotion Organization of Iran Website (September 2023)

In this study efforts have been made to examine EMCs, to identify some of the challenges and barriers they face and propose corresponding solutions for their development and progress.

Research Background

Investigations indicate that domestic studies conducted in the field of export intermediaries, particularly Export Management Companies have primarily focused on their introduction, benefits, and applications. However, fewer studies have delved deeper with the aim of identifying developmental barriers and conducting strategic studies in this area. Some of these studies will be mentioned below:

Howard (1994) by studying 110 Export Management Companies across the United States, concluded that for successful export market information and communication with foreign markets are the most important factors. Additionally, the study identified political risks and human resource sales management as challenging factors for the entry of Export Management Companies into global markets. Shamshiri (2006) introduced and emphasized the benefits of Export Management Companies, highlighting the necessity of conscious efforts towards identifying and prioritizing the requirements of economic enterprises. Ghareche and Shamshiri (2010) emphasized the significance of formulating and prioritizing strategies for meeting the economic needs of enterprises. They considered any deliberate effort towards this goal, by identifying and prioritizing the requirements of economic enterprises as essential. Moshabaki and Khademi (2012) explored the direct and indirect effects of government export development programs on the export performance of firms. They found that these programs not only impact internal factors but also affect the export performance of firms. Sharma (2013) examined the relationship between export management companies and sellers, emphasizing that the lack of trust significantly affects this relationship. The study proposed that strengthening trust between the parties is a crucial strategy in the field of e-commerce. Suwannarat (2016) in a study conducted with the help of the Ministry of Commerce and the Thai Export Development Agency, investigated the direct and indirect effects of export knowledge, communication skills, expertise and credibility on the performance of export intermediaries. The study revealed that these factors implicitly affect the performance of export intermediaries by creating capabilities to reduce transaction costs for customers. The Institute for Trade Studies and Research (2017) introduced Export Management Companies and highlighted their position in countries such as Japan, South Korea, China and the United States. They analyzed the challenges and barriers to the growth of Export Management Companies in Iran, categorizing them into internal (production) and governmental (environmental) barriers. Nikan (2017) with the study of Export Management Companies and knowledge-based SMEs have proposed solutions for export development of knowledge-based companies, focusing on export management companies. According to him, creating and supporting specialized Export Management Companies, especially through financial assistance from the Government can enhance management efficiency, reduce existing costs and consequently facilitate the development of exports. RastinehJavan (2018) examined the challenges and problematic factors facing active Export Management Companies in the Ilam province. Challenges were categorized into political, environmental infrastructure, financial, managerial, and educational issues. The study highlighted the importance of government actions and support in addressing these challenges and facilitating the expansion of exports in the region, especially in the Mehran border market. Dadkhah and Zarepour (2019) explored the major barriers to the development of Export Management Companies through the examination of experts, specialists and practitioners in the field of export and export services in Iran. They

identified 10 significant barriers and proposed solutions to overcome them. The Parliament Research Center Of IRAN (2020) identified problems and challenges in non-oil exports proposing solutions including the utilization of Export Management Companies' services and encouraging small exporters to use these companies. They emphasized the role of EMCs in facilitating the export of goods. Shekarchian (2020) identified the capabilities of Export Management Companies and highlighted the need for SMEs to benefit from the services and capabilities of these companies. She emphasized the significance of collaboration between SMEs and EMCs. Pourmirza et al. (2020) evaluated export readiness components in SMEs. They asserted that executing and improving export readiness in SMEs depends on a comprehensive strategy addressing all identified factors. Lack of export skills and readiness is considered a significant factor contributing to the export failures of these enterprises. Khalili et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between logistics services of companies and export development programs. They found that logistics services, including procurement, packaging, distribution and transportation influence the export performance of companies through the implementation of export development programs. They emphasized that finding export solutions and in general acquiring export knowledge among professionals is impactful. Noori (2023) through a strategic study examined the Export Management Companies in Khorasan Razavi province in Iran. He identified and diagnosed their strengths (22 indicators), weaknesses (30 indicators), opportunities (31 indicators) and threats (52 indicators) and provided strategies for overcoming these challenges.

Methodology

This study utilizes a mixed-methods (quantitative-qualitative) approach and is categorized as applied and descriptive-survey based on its objectives and methods. Qualitative data collection involves fieldwork using interview tools, while quantitative data collection employs questionnaires. The statistical population comprises professionals and stakeholders in the export domain, including export management companies, some export intermediaries, exporters, officials from executive bodies, and other informed experts in export affairs. Accordingly, 18 individuals were purposively selected for qualitative interviews based on their significant experience or expertise in export-related processes and services.

Figure 1: Statistical population of the research

The identification of barriers to the activities of export management companies in this research was conducted through specialized interviews, utilizing the content analysis identification method. After completing the interviews, content implementation and initial note-taking were performed to familiarize with and obtain an overview of the

collected data. Subsequently, significant sections of the interview content were extracted and coded for highlighting purposes. Patterns among the defined codes were identified, and after categorizing them into expressions or themes, they were named and recorded. To ensure the accuracy of the collected data, feedback on the identified data was sought through judgment from some of the interviewees. The finalized qualitative data were considered in preparation for prioritization and subsequent analyses in the form of questionnaires within a Likert scale of 5 options, involving the participation of 25 individuals from the study's population. The Friedman test was employed to rank the data and the results will be further detailed in the following sections.

Findings

Corresponding to the conducted qualitative interviews a total of 48 barriers to the activities of Export Management Companies were identified. These barriers were ultimately categorized into six groups within the two main sections of internal and external barriers as detailed in Table 2. The ranking of identified barriers was conducted through the Friedman test. (Tables 3 to 5)

Table 2. Barriers for Activities of Export Management Companies

Internal Barriers	External Barriers
Performance Barriers (P)	Barriers with Exporters Society Origin (E)
Managerial Barriers (M)	Barriers with Government and Policy-making Origin (G)
Skill Barriers (S)	Barriers with Common Origin (C)

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics - Variables of the Study (Barriers)

Descriptive Statistics								
Test Variables (Barriers)	N	Max	Min	Std. Dev	Mean	Percentile		
						25th	50th	75th
P	25	4.38	2.50	0.64086	3.6368	3.0000	4.0000	4.1300
M	25	4.89	2.56	0.65777	3.9388	3.6150	4.0000	4.5000
S	25	5.00	2.71	0.64565	3.9752	3.6400	4.1400	4.5700
E	25	4.50	3.25	0.38406	3.7800	3.5000	3.7500	4.0000
G	25	4.67	2.93	0.48935	3.9180	3.6350	3.8000	4.3650
C	25	4.80	2.60	0.70682	3.8720	3.4000	4.0000	4.6000

Table 4. Final Results of Friedman Test

N	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
25	14.953	5	0.011

The results from the test in Table 4 indicate a noticeable difference in the mean ranks of the test variables (identified barriers) in terms of their importance. In other words, with a p-value of 0.011, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, there is a statistically significant difference in the perceived importance of the questionnaire items. According to the respondents, these questions are not equally valued and exhibit a significant distinction in importance.

The median values obtained in Table 5 indicate the importance of the identified indicators and determine the ranking position of each barrier in the ranking process. In this way, skill and management barriers arising from internal organizational factors, with median values of 4.30 and 3.84, hold the highest importance and rank first and second. Following these, three other barriers from the set of external factors centered on governance and policy-making origin factors, common origin factors and exporter society origin factors with median values of 3.58, 3.56 and 3.34 respectively occupy the third to fifth ranks. Finally, performance-origin barriers from the set of internal organizational factors with a median value of 2.38 hold the sixth and final rank.

Table 5. Ranking of Barriers for Activities of Export Management Companies

Barriers		(Mean Rank)	Rank
Internal factors	Skill Barriers (S)	4.30	1
	Managerial Barriers (M)	3.84	2
External factors	Barriers with Government and Policy-making Origin (G)	3.58	3
	Barriers with Common Origin (C)	3.56	4
	Barriers with Exporters Society Origin (E)	3.34	5
Internal factors	Performance Barriers (P)	2.38	6

Discussion and Conclusion

Utilizing the capacities of export intermediaries particularly Export Management Companies as a well-established and globally successful strategy holds special importance in alleviating a significant portion of export challenges and facilitating export expansion. Recognizing this significance, the current research endeavors to identify and prioritize the barriers for activities of Export Management Companies and propose solutions aimed at addressing these barriers.

Based on this and aim to response the primary research question, 48 barriers were identified. These barriers were categorized into two main categories of internal and external factors, as detailed in Table 2 and the following specifics.

Performance Barriers

1. Insufficient familiarity with the technical knowledge of export product.
2. Lack of adequate mastery over the laws of foreign trade of target markets.
3. Weakness in introducing and proving the EMCs effectiveness to the exporting community of the country.
4. Weakness in organizing events and sending/receiving trade delegations.
5. Lack of active presence in domestic and international exhibition opportunities.

6. Sole reliance on internet studies rather than field research and effective presence in target markets.
7. Failure to leverage e-commerce platforms and information technology in export management processes.
8. Conducting personal business activities alongside export services.

Managerial Barriers

1. Short-term results-oriented approach instead of formulating medium and long-term strategies.
2. Neglecting knowledge management and the transfer of experience to peers and other export management practitioners.
3. Insufficient attention to research and development (R&D) activities and studying successful international models.
4. Sole reliance on one individual in executing export management processes in most export management companies.
5. Insufficient utilization of specialized human resources in export management.
6. Financial constraints in executing export management processes.
7. Weakness in networking and establishing effective communications with other EMCs and exporters.
8. Weakness in networking and establishing effective international-level communications.
9. Failure to engage in activities within a specific product or specific market.

Skill Barriers

1. Weakness in managing the final price of export processes.
2. Weakness in formulating Export Readiness Assistance (ERA) programs for exporters.
3. Lack of proficiency and familiarity with exporter collaboration models.
4. Weakness in efficient management of export processes.
5. Weakness in contracting export management service agreements with exporters.
6. Weakness in formulating and implementing market retention strategies.
7. Weakness in conducting proper market research.

Barriers with Exporters Society Origin

1. Zero-to-hundred approach in export processes by most exporters instead of outsourcing.

2. Low flexibility of the exporting community in adapting to the requirements of target export markets.

3. Formation of most production units in the country based on the domestic market and lacking an export-oriented perspective.

4. Low inclination to enter higher-level markets due to having sales in less prominent neighboring markets.

- *Barriers with Government and Policy-making Origin:*

1. Currency fluctuations and instability within the country.

2. Absence of a professional and organizational perspective on the activities of EMCs in the country.

3. Lack of a coherent legal framework in the formation and operation of EMCs.

4. Lack of attractive incentives and privileges for the activities of EMCs.

5. Disinterest of most EMCs in renewing and upgrading their ranks due to unmet supportive expectations.

6. Failure to utilize consultative opinions of practitioners in the field of export management alongside trade advisors for better export management in the country.

7. Excessive administrative bureaucracy in many foreign trade processes, especially exports.

8. Difficulty in obtaining bank facilities and attracting financial support for export.

9. Lack of stability in supportive approaches towards SMEs compared to large companies, corresponding to changes in governments.

10. Absence of specific legislation for EMCs considering the roles of various executive bodies in the country and determining necessary support from them.

11. Insufficient attention to promoting knowledge and culture export in the country.

12. Weak role of the Trade Promotion Organization of Iran (TPO) in formulating Extra-organizational regulations for the development of EMCs.

13. Lack of an approved budget specifically allocated for the quantitative and qualitative development of EMCs.

14. Weakness in implementation of incentive policies for exporters and export intermediaries.

15. Sudden changes in effective laws and regulations on foreign trade especially exports.

Barriers with Common Origin

1. Higher total cost of Iranian export goods compared to global competitors.
2. Lack of sufficient trust between exporters and EMCs.
3. Insufficient awareness in the country's export community regarding the nature of entities called EMCs.
4. Lack of commercial centers and showrooms for Iranian goods in target markets.
5. Weakness in conducting collective activities in the form of associations and export holdings in most Iranian companies.

In order to answer the first sub-question of the research, the identified barriers were ranked using the Friedman test. (Table 5)

In order to answer the second sub-question of the research the following solutions are proposed to overcome barriers for activities of Export Management Companies and to facilitate their quantitative and qualitative development:

Proposed Solutions for Overcoming Internal Barriers

1. Emphasis on employing strategic and planned approaches in export management activities and processes and avoiding short-term result-oriented approaches.
2. Utilizing pricing management methods for export processes and products along with reducing and eliminating unnecessary items.
3. Studying successful global models in the field of export intermediary services to enhance skills related to export management.
4. Maximizing the utilization of specialists in the field of export management.
5. Securing financial resources through attracting investor participation (financial crowdfunding).
6. Outsourcing some export processes to other export intermediaries.
7. Establish long-term and exclusive contracts with foreign distributors and channels.
8. Forming strategic alliances or consortia with other EMCs.

9. Adopting a focused approach, either product or geography in export management or both (specialized product for a specific target market).

10. Strive to enhance the technical knowledge of export products.

11. Make efforts to introduce oneself and capabilities to export audiences through various means, including launching a bilingual website, advertising, and appropriate presentations in different visual and auditory media, etc.

12. Give importance to organizing and actively participating in domestic and international trade fairs and events.

13. Utilizing the high capacity of information technology and the internet to expand penetration in target markets.

Proposed Solutions for Overcoming External Barriers

1. Focusing on enhancing knowledge and culture export.

2. Eliminate or reduce unnecessary administrative bureaucracy in export management processes.

3. Utilizing the advisory opinions of successful and experienced EMCs in formulating and implementing the country's export policies.

4. Eliminating difficulties related to providing financial facilities to EMCs.

5. Drafting a specialized law for the establishment, operation and development of EMCs considering the roles of various executive bodies of the country.

6. Organizing and removing currency-related barriers particularly in export and export processes.

7. Allocating and granting attractive and diverse incentives to EMCs based on their obtained ranking.

8. Allocating and granting various incentives to the export community for outsourcing export processes to intermediaries and EMCs instead of handling everything independently by the exporters themselves.

9. Facilitating for a deeper understanding of EMCs and their services within the export community.

10. Adopting policies to establish and develop trade centers and showrooms for Iranian goods in target markets.

11. Striving to build trust and foster working interactions between the export community and EMCs through various means.

The downward trend in the number of Export Management Companies as evidenced by the ranking program of the Trade Promotion Organization of Iran (TPO) in recent years highlights significant structural challenges in both internal factors (internal weaknesses of companies) and external factors (nationally and internationally) that requires focused attention in both areas. Therefore, actions and solutions for the development of Export Management Companies on one hand should be directed towards addressing internal weaknesses and strengthening these companies and on the other hand should be focused on reducing external threats, obstacles, and their effects.

Comparison of the results obtained from this research with other reviewed studies in terms of the categorization of barriers faced by exporters to internal and external markets aligns with the findings of Agnihotri and Bhattacharya (2015), Cavusgil and Zou (1994) and Leonidou (2004); and in terms of the details of this categorization the results are consistent with those of Pinho and Martins (2010). Additionally, an internal study conducted by the Parliament Research Center of Iran (2020) also points to similar findings.

Although this case study was conducted within the confines of Khorasan Razavi province, considering the inherent nature of EMC, the fact that their activities are not limited to the geography of their establishment within the country, the similarity in how all of them are influenced by external factors present in the country's foreign trade ecosystem especially exports and the expert opinions of the participants in this study, it seems that the identified barriers can be generalized to the entire community of EMCs in the country and the recommended solutions can be considered for all of them.

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